

Alkali Iron Phosphates as An Efficient Oxygen Reduction Electrocatalysts

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Abstract:

Water-Splitting systems are essential for clean energy production. The oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) is a key reaction involved in water splitting, which requires a catalyst. The current work explores the possible application of sodium and potassium iron phosphates ($A\text{FePO}_4$, $A = \text{Na}$, and K) as electrocatalysts for ORR activity. These earth-abundant iron phosphates were synthesized by solution combustion synthesis (SCS) technique using ascorbic acid both as fuel and reducing agent for Fe. The crystal structure was analyzed by Rietveld refinement. The formation of carbon coating was identified by thermogravimetric analysis and Raman spectroscopy. Electrocatalytic properties of $A\text{FePO}_4$ was investigated in alkali electrolytes for the first time by using linear sweep voltammetry with rotating disk electrode (RDE). The oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) activities of these alkali iron phosphates are comparable to that of Pt/C system. The Tafel slope and electron transfer number of the alkali iron phosphates were calculated. The ORR activity of NaFePO_4 was found to be better than KFePO_4 and FePO_4 . This work demonstrates alkali iron phosphates as alternate cost-effective, novel electrocatalysts for productive ORR activity in alkaline solution.

Keywords: $A\text{FePO}_4$, Electrocatalyst, Oxygen reduction reaction, Earth-abundant, crystal structure.

References:

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